

Online Learning for Intelligent Thermal Management of Interference-coupled and Passively Cooled Base Stations

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Abstract—Passively cooled base stations (PCBSs) have emerged to deliver better cost and energy efficiency. However, passive cooling necessitates intelligent thermal control via traffic management, i.e., the instantaneous data traffic or throughput of a PCBS directly impacts its thermal performance. This is particularly challenging for outdoor deployment of PCBSs because the heat dissipation efficiency is uncertain and fluctuates over time. What is more, the PCBSs are interference-coupled in multi-cell scenarios. Thus, a higher-throughput PCBS leads to higher interference to the other PCBSs, which, in turn, would require more resource consumption to meet their respective throughput targets. In this paper, we address online decision-making for maximizing the total downlink throughput for a multi-PCBS system subject to constraints related on operating temperature. We demonstrate that a reinforcement learning (RL) approach, specifically soft actor-critic (SAC), can successfully perform throughput maximization while keeping the PCBSs cool, by adapting the throughput to time-varying heat dissipation conditions. Furthermore, we design a denial and reward mechanism that effectively mitigates the risk of overheating during the exploration phase of RL. Simulation results show that our approach achieves up to 88.6% of the global optimum. This is very promising, as our approach operates without prior knowledge of future heat dissipation efficiency, which is required by the global optimum.

Index Terms—Reinforcement learning, interference, passive cooling, throughput maximization, thermal management.

1 INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of 5G networks has increased data, but also energy consumption. As a result, operators face higher operational expenses. The study in [2] shows that active cooling consumes up to 40% of the total energy usage by mobile networks. Recently, the concept of passively cooled base stations (PCBSs) has emerged [3]. Unlike traditional base stations, a PCBS uses passive cooling solutions, such as highly thermally conductive fillers (e.g., graphene, carbon nanotubes), to keep the equipment in the base stations within an acceptable temperature range, thus eliminating the energy cost due to active cooling.

A 5G base station (BS) basically consists of a distribution unit (DU) and a radio unit (RU). It should be noted that a key source of heat generation in BS is the baseband processor in the DU. The processor is responsible for handling a large volume of complex signal processing tasks, including modulation/demodulation and encoding/decoding. By PCBS' nature, managing the thermal performance becomes crucial. The amount of heat generation of a baseband processor

directly affects the amount of traffic, or data throughput, that the PCBS is delivering.

Ideally, we would like to have a PCBS deliver as much throughput as possible while avoiding overheating. This is not an easy task for two reasons. First, the heat dissipation efficiency is an uncertain system parameter for an outdoor PCBS, as it is influenced by ambient temperature, wind speed, humidity, and solar exposure, etc. Second, for a multi-cell scenario, the PCBSs are interference-coupled. Delivering more throughput at one PCBSs means also more frequent transmissions, thus increasing the interference to the other PCBSs, which would have to allocate more time-frequency resource, to meet their respective throughput targets. Hence, we not only need to consider the thermal matter, but also have to ensure that the resource limit is adhered to, accounting for the fact that the consumption of transmission resource of a PCBS depends also on the throughput set by the other PCBSs.

In this paper, we consider an outdoor multi-PCBS system deploying orthogonal frequency-division multiple access (OFDMA) and multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) technology. The goal is to maximize the sum throughput of PCBSs in the downlink, subject to the baseband processors' temperature limit and interference coupling of the PCBSs. This is an online decision-making problem. The baseband processors' temperature evolution is determined by the PCBS' throughput (i.e., the amount of traffic served) and the heat dissipation efficiency. The latter is an uncertain system

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parameter that varies over time. Hence we need to deal with throughput maximization without knowing future heat dissipation efficiency. Our contributions to dealing with this online optimization problem are as follows.

- 1) We propose an online PCBS thermal management method based on a reinforcement learning (RL) approach, specifically soft actor-critic (SAC) [4]. The method maximizes the total downlink throughput adaptively and dynamically, subject to the communication resource and baseband processors' temperature constraints.
- 2) Because of interference coupling, the consumption of time-frequency resource of a PCBS, referred to as load, is affected by, in addition to the PCBS's own throughput, the load of other PCBSs. As a result, throughput maximization cannot be performed separately for each PCBS. We model and analyze this load-coupling system for MIMO transmission, facilitating the evaluation of an action with respect to the required transmission resource in SAC.
- 3) Since exploration in the RL framework may cause overheating of the baseband processor, we provide a refined denial and reward mechanism to ensure that the RL approach can sufficiently explore while preventing baseband processor overheating. This, in fact, enables the RL approach to be used online without any pre-training.
- 4) Simulation shows very promising results. Specifically, the proposed approach delivers up to 88.6% of the global optimum. Note that achieving the global optimum is not possible in practice, as it requires solving a problem offline with complete information of heat dissipation efficiency in future (i.e., an oracle), whereas our method makes decisions online without prior knowledge of future heat dissipation efficiency. In addition, the learned policy has good generalization with respect to user location update.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The works in [5]–[9] have studied passive cooling techniques for base stations. In [5], the authors provide a passive cooling method using sorption-based evaporative cooling with a salt-embedded composite sorbent for 5G communication equipment, to significantly enhance heat dissipation performance. Similarly, in [6], the authors propose a passive thermal management strategy that relies on moisture desorption from hygroscopic salt solutions through a protective membrane that only allows water vapor to pass through. The research in [7] conducted thermal simulations to evaluate the cooling performance of distinct CPU heatsinks. In [8], a novel heat dissipation structure has been designed with antennas and digital beamforming chips on opposite sides, demonstrating superior cooling efficiency compared to traditional designs. Paper [9] explores various factors for efficient PCBS cooling, including environmental influences, strategic placement, and the use of innovative materials.

Furthermore, some works focus on the optimization for passively cooled planar arrays. In [10], a system-driven convex algorithm is proposed for the synthesis of passively cooled planar phased arrays of mm-wave 5G base stations. In [11], a convex optimization algorithm is derived to synthesize the array layouts with minimized side lobes within a pre-defined cell sector.

There are works on thermal management in data centers and wireless communication systems through resource allocation. The study in [12] addresses a holistic energy minimization problem in a data center with an active cooling system. The server temperature is influenced by the thermal load, server inlet cold air temperature, and airflow rate. To ensure reliability, the server temperature must be kept below a threshold, which can be achieved by adjusting parameters such as fan speed. In addition, in a baseband unit (BBU) pool of a cloud radio access network (C-RAN), the authors of [13] provide an algorithm for dynamic allocation of computing resource, integrating thermal characteristics in the optimization of power consumption and computing resource usage, such that the processors work at the proper temperature. In [14], the research highlights the challenge of minimizing computational power while optimizing computing resource usage efficiency under thermal constraints, due to that the static power grows with the operating temperature of core computing unit. The authors present an algorithm that dynamically adjusts voltage and frequency to save power while meeting traffic request deadlines. In [15], the authors propose an optimization framework based on deep reinforcement learning, to jointly optimize energy consumption from the perspectives of task scheduling and cooling control in data centers. Note that the computing resources (i.e., processors) in data centers and C-RAN are centralized in a place far from users. In contrast, thermal management in base stations needs to consider additional matters, such as user demand and signal processing, making it more complex. For example, the work in [16] studies task schedule and resource allocation in a UAV-and-Base-station hybrid-enabled mobile network with a passively cooled system, and with joint optimization of user admission policy, task scheduling, UAV hovering trajectory, traveling time, and computation-and-communication resource allocations.

In addition, both [17] and [18] study traffic and load management of base stations using RL. The study in [17] introduces a deep RL framework for mobility traffic management in cellular networks, utilizing cell individual offset adjustments. Depending on network size, it employs enhanced deep Q-learning or advanced RL methods like deep deterministic policy gradient and twin delayed deep deterministic policy gradient. In [18], the authors introduce a multi-objective RL framework for traffic balancing for multi-band downlink cellular networks. Utilizing meta-RL and policy distillation techniques, the framework is designed to adapt to diverse objective trade-offs quickly. Besides, some research [19]–[22] investigate sleep mode as a load management strategy for base stations. Different from our paper, the above works do not consider the use of passively cooling.

For single PCBS, we have addressed online throughput maximization in [23]. In the current paper, the system model consists of multiple PCBSs, and the resulting optimization problem is much more challenging because the PCBSs are interference-coupled. That is, the resource allocation in one PCBS cell directly affects the performance in the other cells, and thus optimization cannot be done for the individual PCBSs separately. In addition, the extended system model addresses the effect of MIMO. By modeling these aspects to enable to incorporate them in the learning framework, the current paper contains significant extensions of [23].

3 SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

Consider a multi-cell OFDMA MIMO system using PCBSs. The set of cells is denoted by $\mathcal{I} = \{1, 2, \dots, I\}$, and the set of users represented by $\mathcal{J} = \{1, 2, \dots, J\}$. The subset of users in cell i is denoted by \mathcal{J}_i .

3.1 Load Coupling in Multi-cell MIMO Systems

In the downlink, for a PCBS and a user, denote by N_T and N_R the numbers of transmit and receive antennas, respectively. The communication takes place over discrete resource blocks (RBs), each having bandwidth B . The wireless channel from PCBS i to user j is narrowband and time-invariant, and it is characterized by an $N_R \times N_T$ matrix $\mathbf{H}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_T}$. The transmitted symbol vector $\mathbf{x}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T \times 1}$ is comprised by N_T independent input symbols $x_{ij,1}, x_{ij,2}, \dots, x_{ij,N_T}$.

We remark that via RAN planning, inter-cell interference among adjacent cells can be significantly reduced with low radio frequency reuse. However, this would limit the available bandwidth of the BSs and result in lower overall data throughput [24], [25]. Therefore, the interference scenario we study is of relevance, even though it may not represent universally practical network deployments. It is worth pointing out that, to provide adequate service to cell-edge users, fractional frequency reuse and soft frequency reuse schemes adopting different reuse factors for cell center and edge users have been proposed [26]–[28]. Our system model can be generalized to such schemes, by splitting the available time-frequency resource and introducing two separate sets of load variables. Thus the received signal at user j from PCBS i , $\mathbf{y}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times 1}$, can be expressed in matrix form as

$$\mathbf{y}_{ij} = \underbrace{\sqrt{\frac{E}{N_T}} \mathbf{H}_{ij} \mathbf{x}_{ij}}_{\text{signal}} + \underbrace{\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{J}_\ell} \sqrt{\frac{E}{N_T}} \mathbf{H}_{\ell j} \mathbf{x}_{\ell k}}_{\text{interference}} + \underbrace{\mathbf{z}_j}_{\text{noise}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{\ell j}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{\ell j}$ denote the channel matrix and transmitted symbol vector by BS ℓ to user j , respectively, E signifies the power of transmitted signals, and $\mathbf{z}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times 1}$ represents the noise vector, which is assumed to be zero-mean circular symmetric complex Gaussian (ZMCSCG). We assume that the transmission power for each transmit antenna is one unit, such that we have the following constraint,

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{x}_{ij} \mathbf{x}_{ij}^T) = N_T. \quad (2)$$

As commented earlier, the amount of RBs needed by one PCBS is coupled with that of the other PCBSs due to the inter-cell interference. Henceforth, we use the term load to refer to the amount of RB consumption of a cell. (Note that this entity is different from the data throughput.) Apparently, the load is directly proportional to how frequent transmissions occur. Hence load is tightly connected to interference generation. At the two extremes, zero load means no transmission and hence no interference, and 100% load means full occupation of all RBs, and hence another PCBS will receive inter-cell interference, no matter which RBs to use. To some extent, load represents the likelihood of interference. In so called load-coupling model, the load of an interfering cell is incorporated into the denominator of the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR), in form of a scaling parameter in front of interference. This interference modeling approach has been widely used in various context, see, e.g., [29]–[37], and its accuracy has been demonstrated in [30], [33], among others. In the current paper, we extend the model to our MIMO setting.

We remark that the load of a cell is the sum of that for serving each of its users. For a user, the corresponding value is determined by the user throughput and SINR. The latter, by the load-coupling model, depends on the load levels of other cells. This is the reason why the cell load levels are coupled, and the relation is given by a non-linear system. Let $\rho_{\ell k} \in [0, 1]$ represent the load of cell ℓ due to serving user k . With the load-coupling model, the interference received at another user j in another cell i is given by

$$\Phi_{ij} = \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{J}_\ell} \rho_{\ell k} \frac{E}{N_T} \|\mathbf{H}_{\ell j} \mathbf{x}_{\ell k}\|^2. \quad (3)$$

Intuitively, $\rho_{\ell k}$ reflects the likelihood that a user outside cell ℓ receives interference from cell ℓ due to that cell ℓ serves its user k . Therefore, the SINR for user j in cell i is given by

$$\text{SINR}_{ij} = \frac{\frac{E}{N_T} \|\mathbf{H}_{ij} \mathbf{x}_{ij}\|^2}{\Phi_{ij} + BN_0}, \quad (4)$$

where N_0 is the noise power spectral density.

For user j in cell i , the rate on one RB is $B \log(1 + \text{SINR}_{ij})$. Hence, to deliver throughput D_{ij} , we obtain the following

$$D_{ij} = \rho_{ij} B \log(1 + \text{SINR}_{ij}) \quad (5)$$

Note that the above system contains the transmit vectors to be designed, as well as the load values that are coupled with each other with non-linear relations. Additionally, let D_i represent the total throughput of cell i , which is bounded by the capacity of the baseband processor:

$$D_i \leq D^{\max}. \quad (6)$$

3.2 Thermal Dynamics of PCBS

We consider slotted time, and denote the time horizon under consideration by time slot set $\mathcal{T} = \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$. The

duration of each time slot, denoted by δ , is flexible ¹. For PCBS i , each time slot t is characterized by the baseband processor's temperature Ψ_i^t , updated at the beginning of the slot. Subsequently, the term "temperature" (with unit Celsius) refers to the baseband processor's temperature, and the ambient temperature is denoted by $\hat{\Psi}_i^t$.

The interplay between heat generation and heat dissipation governs the thermal dynamics of the PCBS. Let $P_i^{\uparrow t}$ denote the heat generated and $P_i^{\downarrow t}$ the heat dissipated in time slot t , measured in watts (W). Based on fundamental heat transfer principles [38], the temperature evolution can be described by

$$\Psi_i^{t+1} = \Psi_i^t + \lambda_i \delta (P_i^{\uparrow t} - P_i^{\downarrow t}), \quad (7)$$

where λ_i (in °C/Joule) represents the reciprocal of the thermal capacitance of the baseband processor of PCBS i . Thermal capacitance is the amount of heat required to cause a unit increase in the temperature. The generation of heat $P_i^{\uparrow t}$, is linked to the baseband processor power consumption, comprising both dynamic power $P_i^{\zeta t}$ and static power $P_i^{\theta t}$ components [39], in watts:

$$P_i^{\uparrow t} = P_i^{\zeta t} + P_i^{\theta t}. \quad (8)$$

Dynamic power consumption $P_i^{\zeta t}$ is directly proportional to the computational workload of PCBS i in time slot t . For time slot t , we use $D_i^t = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} D_{ij}^t$, where D_{ij}^t is the throughput of user j , to represent the throughput of cell i . For PCBS i , the dynamic power can be expressed as [40]

$$P_i^{\zeta t} = \mu_i D_i^t, \quad (9)$$

where μ_i (in Watt/bit) is a coefficient specific to the baseband processor of PCBS i . Conversely, static power consumption $P_i^{\theta t}$ exhibits an exponential relationship with the processor's temperature [39], [41], which is described by

$$P_i^{\theta t} = \alpha_i e^{\beta_i \Psi_i^t} + \gamma_i, \quad (10)$$

where α_i , β_i , and γ_i are parameters that characterize the material properties of the processor. This exponential relationship occurs because as the temperature increases, leakage currents within the processor's transistors rise exponentially, leading to higher static power consumption [40].

Heat dissipation efficiency for time slot t , denoted by $\sigma_i^t > 0$, is affected by the temperature difference between the processor and its surroundings. A higher efficiency indicates that the system cools down more quickly. Following Newton's law of cooling [38], the dissipated power is given by

$$P_i^{\downarrow t} = \sigma_i^t (\Psi_i^t - \hat{\Psi}_i^t). \quad (11)$$

Based on (7)-(11), the temperature at the start of time slot $t + 1$ (or the end of slot t) can be determined by:

$$\Psi_i^{t+1}$$

1. A slotted time horizon is reasonable because decision-making and updates in mobile networks naturally occur at discrete intervals. Moreover, a time slot length on the order of one second is sufficiently short to achieve the accuracy needed for thermal management.

Fig. 1: A processor temperature evolution and the accumulated throughput under three different throughput policies.

$$= \max \left\{ \Psi_i^t + \lambda_i \delta \left[\mu_i D_i^t + \alpha_i e^{\beta_i \Psi_i^t} + \gamma_i - \sigma_i^t (\Psi_i^t - \hat{\Psi}_i^t) \right], \hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1} \right\}. \quad (12)$$

We can see from (12) that the baseband processor's temperature does not fall below the ambient temperature. A critical operational constraint is to maintain the baseband processor's temperature below a safe threshold, $\bar{\Psi}$, across all time slots,

$$\Psi_i^t \leq \bar{\Psi}, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (13)$$

By (8)-(10), we can adjust the throughput delivered by the baseband processor in every time slot to control the processor temperature of a PCBS. We illustrate three throughput policies, i.e., thermal management strategies, in Fig. 1 as examples, to show the trade-off between throughput and temperature. Here, the throughput represents the accumulated value. For the illustration, 120°C is the maximum allowable temperature of the processor.

- 1) **Aggressive policy:** Under this policy, the baseband processor always attempts to handle the maximum possible workload. As a result, the baseband processor continuously generates heat exceeding the amount of heat dissipation, causing overheating. The throughput is higher than the two other policies at the beginning but cannot be sustained.
- 2) **Conservative policy:** With this policy, the baseband processor delivers only a small amount of throughput, allowing the generated heat to dissipate within each time slot. This keeps the processor temperature around 50°C. However, as can be seen, the conservative action results in rather low throughput.
- 3) **(Naive) Adaptive policy:** This policy adapts the throughput to the temperature evolution. The temperature curve is in fact what we would normally expect from thermal management. However, note that the policy is still somewhat naive because it periodically sets the throughput to be zero for some time slots (shown

by the plateaus in the accumulated throughput curve) to allow the baseband processor to cool down.

Remark 1. *The adaptive policy may be seemingly easy to design. This is however not the case for two reasons. First, the heat dissipation efficiency of future time slots is not known in an online setting. Second, the throughput of the cells, as discussed earlier, cannot be set separately, because they together determine the radio resource consumption, i.e., load, and we need to ensure this consumption does not exceed what is available.*

3.3 Problem Formulation

For problem formulation of throughput maximization, we now denote explicitly the SINR_{ij} as function of \mathbf{x}_{ij}^t and interference Φ_{ij}^t , as $\text{SINR}_{ij}^t(\mathbf{x}_{ij}^t, \Phi_{ij}^t)$. Note that Φ_{ij}^t is a function Φ_{ij}^t depends on $\mathbf{x}_{\ell k}^t$ and the load values $\rho_{\ell k}^t$, $k \in \mathcal{J}_\ell, \ell \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i\}$. To ensure fairness, we impose a constraint that in each time slot, the throughput of every user must not fall below a certain threshold. This threshold is defined as the total throughput of the user's serving cell divided by the number of users in the cell. Thus, we have the following constraint:

$$\rho_{ij}^t B \log [1 + \text{SINR}_{ij}^t(\mathbf{x}_{ij}^t, \Phi_{ij}^t)] \geq \frac{D_i^t}{|\mathcal{J}_i|}, j \in \mathcal{J}_i, i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (14)$$

where ρ_{ij}^t is the the proportion of time-frequency resources allocated to user j in cell i in time slot t .

We use ρ_i^t and Ψ_i^t to represent the level (or proportion) of time-frequency resources used at PCBS i and the baseband processor's temperature of PCBS i in time slot t , respectively. As mentioned earlier, our problem is of online decision-making. For the sake of presentation, however, let us for a moment assume that the heat dissipation coefficients of all time slots are known in advance. The problem can then be formulated as follows.

$$\max \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} D_i^t \quad (15a)$$

$$\text{o.v. } D_i^t \in [0, D_i^{\max}], \mathbf{x}_{ij}^t, \rho_{ij}^t, \rho_i^t, \Psi_i^t, i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}_i, t \in \mathcal{T}$$

$$\text{s.t. } \Psi_i^{t+1} \geq \Psi_i^t + \lambda_i \delta [\mu_i D_i^t + \alpha_i e^{\beta_i \Psi_i^t} + \gamma_i - \sigma_i^t (\Psi_i^t - \hat{\Psi}_i^t)], \\ i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T} \setminus \{T\} \quad (15b)$$

$$\hat{\Psi}_i^t \leq \Psi_i^t \leq \bar{\Psi}_i, i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15c)$$

$$\rho_{ij}^t B \log [1 + \text{SINR}_{ij}^t(\mathbf{x}_{ij}^t, \Phi_{ij}^t)] \geq \frac{D_i^t}{|\mathcal{J}_i|}, \\ j \in \mathcal{J}_i, i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15d)$$

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{x}_{ij}^t \mathbf{x}_{ij}^{t \top}) = N_T, j \in \mathcal{J}_i, i \in \mathcal{I} \quad (15e)$$

$$\rho_i^t = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \rho_{ij}^t \leq \bar{\rho}, i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15f)$$

For a system with PCBSs, where cooling energy consumption has been eliminated, our primary objective is to maximize the total system throughput across all time slots, as outlined in (15a). This ensures efficient resource utilization, especially during busy traffic hours. We acknowledge, however, that in scenarios with lower demand, such as

during nighttime, minimizing energy consumption may be a more appropriate goal. The constraints in (15b) and (15c) address the thermal dynamics of the passive cooling system, ensuring that base stations operate within safe temperature limits. Additionally, constraint (15f) ensures that time-frequency resource consumption, governed by the nonlinear system in (15d), adheres to the resource limit $\bar{\rho}$ across all cells.

To facilitate ease of reference, Table 1 presents all notations along with their corresponding definitions.

TABLE 1: Notations and definitions

Notation	Definition
\mathcal{I}	Set of cells
\mathcal{J}	Set of users
\mathcal{J}_i	Subset of users in cell i
N_T	Number of transmit antennas
N_R	Number of receive antennas
B	Bandwidth of each resource block
\mathbf{H}_{ij}	Channel matrix from PCBS i to user j
\mathbf{x}_{ij}	Transmitted symbol vector from PCBS i to user j
\mathbf{y}_{ij}	Received signal by user j in PCBS i
E	Power of transmitted signals
\mathbf{z}_j	Noise vector
$\rho_{\ell k}$	Load of cell ℓ due to serving user k
Φ_{ij}	Interference received by user j in cell i
N_0	Noise power spectral density
SINR_{ij}	SINR for user j in cell i
D_{ij}	Throughput for user j in cell i
D_i	Total throughput of cell i
D_i^{\max}	Maximum throughput capacity of a cell
\mathcal{T}	Set of time slots
δ	Duration of each time slot
Ψ_i^t	Processor's temperature of PCBS i in time slot t
$\hat{\Psi}_i^t$	Ambient temperature in time slot t
$P_i^{\uparrow t}$	The amount of heat generated in time slot t
$P_i^{\downarrow t}$	The amount of heat dissipated in time slot t
λ_i	Reciprocal of the thermal capacitance of PCBS i
$P_i^{s t}$	Dynamic power consumption in time slot t
$P_i^{\text{st} t}$	Static power consumption in time slot t
μ_i	Dynamic power coefficient of PCBS i
$\alpha_i, \beta_i, \gamma_i$	Parameters characterizing static power consumption
σ_i^t	Heat dissipation efficiency in time slot t
$\bar{\Psi}_i$	Safe threshold for processor's temperature
ρ_{ij}^t	Load fo cell i due to serving user j in time slot t
$\bar{\rho}$	Maximum allowable resource consumption in a cell

4 ALGORITHM DESIGN: OVERVIEW

The problem in (15) presents challenges due to the cells' interdependence in load and the non-convex nature of (15d). Moreover, for online decision-making, we do not have the parameter values of all time slots in order to have (15) in its complete form. Although proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controllers are commonly used for thermal management [42], they face several limitations in this context. PID controllers well in linear and relatively simple systems. However, in more complex and nonlinear environments, their performance may be limited and may not fully meet the system's requirements. Improper tuning can lead to temperature oscillations, risking overheating, whereas RL

adapts dynamically to balance safety and performance. Moreover, PID might not be suitable for our multi-agent scenario, which requires coordination across multiple base stations. Therefore, we adopt RL for problem-solving.

The goal of the algorithm design of RL is to provide a policy enabling to schedule throughput effectively across various states by maximizing the long-term cumulative reward. To this end, we model the multi-cell system as an agent, and the action of the agent consists of the variables to be optimized. The fundamental components of this agent are as follows.

4.1 State and Action

Based on (15b)-(15c), for a given time slot t , the agent needs access the current system specifics, which encompass

- Ambient temperature, $\hat{\Psi}_i^t, i \in \mathcal{I}$,
- Processor temperature, $\Psi_i^t, i \in \mathcal{I}$,
- Optionally, the heat dissipation efficiency, $\sigma_i^t, i \in \mathcal{I}$.

Note that if a time slot is short, then it is reasonable to assume that the heat dissipation efficiency at the very beginning of a time slot remains for the entire slot duration; otherwise, we may not assume the knowledge of heat dissipation for the current time slot. Therefore we consider two scenarios:

- 1) Informed-Heat-Dissipation (IHD) Scenario: In this case, PCBS knows the heat dissipation efficiency for the current time slot. Thus, the state s_t in the time slot t is expressed by

$$s_t = \left[\left(\hat{\Psi}_i^t, \Psi_i^t, \sigma_i^t \right), i \in \mathcal{I} \right]. \quad (16)$$

- 2) Uninformed-Heat-Dissipation (UHD) Scenario: In contrast, the heat dissipation efficiency is not known, so we utilize s'_t to delineate its state as:

$$s'_t = \left[\left(\hat{\Psi}_i^t, \Psi_i^t \right), i \in \mathcal{I} \right]. \quad (17)$$

With state s_t in time slot t , the agent takes an action in action space. The action a_t is defined as

$$a_t = [D_i^t, i \in \mathcal{I}]. \quad (18)$$

4.2 Reward Mechanism

We employ soft actor-critic (SAC) to refine policies with the aim of maximizing rewards in the environment [4]. SAC finds the maximum of the expected sum of rewards and takes the expected entropy objective to adopt stochastic policies. The maximum entropy objective function is defined as:

$$J(\pi) = \sum_{t=0}^T \mathbb{E}_{(s_t, a_t) \sim \rho_\pi} [R(s_t, a_t) + kH(\pi(\cdot|s_t))], \quad (19)$$

where $R(s_t, a_t)$ is the reward function, k is a factor to determine the importance of entropy relative to the reward, and $\pi(\cdot|s_t)$ is the probability distribution of subsequent actions given the state s_t , typically resorting to a Gaussian distribution. Additionally, $H(\pi(\cdot|s_t))$ embodies the entropy

component, represented as $H(\pi(\cdot|s_t)) \triangleq \mathbb{E}_a [-\log(\pi(a|s_t))]$. It is important to highlight that the agent actively tries various actions to maximize the target entropy. This strategy improves the exploratory feature of SAC.

Our design of the reward mechanism is comprised of two elements.

- 1) Design for resource constraint (15f): Should the agent initiate an action to set the throughput levels such that the resulting load in any cell exceeds resource availability, the action will not be executed, leading to a reward of zero for the agent. Conversely, if the action is within the resource limit, the agent may be given a positive reward.
- 2) Design for temperature constraint (15c): In the event that an action proposed by the agent leads to the estimated CPU temperature exceeding the maximum allowed threshold, the action will be rejected, and the agent will receive no reward. On the other hand, actions that maintain the baseband processor's temperature within safe limits will be rewarded with a positive value. We will present a refinement of this basic design later on.

5 REWARD DESIGN FOR RESOURCE LIMIT

5.1 Preliminaries

In the context of RL, the resource constraint (15f) boils down to the following: For an action $\{D_i^t | i \in \mathcal{I}\}$, can these throughput levels be met within the resource limit? This amounts to the following min-max problem. For simplicity, the time slot index is omitted.

$$\min \hat{\rho} \quad (20a)$$

$$\text{o.v. } \hat{\rho}, \mathbf{x}_{ij}, \rho_{ij}, i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}_i$$

$$\text{s.t. } \rho_{ij} B \log [1 + \text{SINR}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_{ij}, \Phi_{ij})] \geq \frac{D_i}{|\mathcal{J}_i|}, j \in \mathcal{J}_i, i \in \mathcal{I} \quad (20b)$$

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{x}_{ij} \mathbf{x}_{ij}^T) = N_T, j \in \mathcal{J}_i, i \in \mathcal{I} \quad (20c)$$

$$\rho_i = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \rho_{ij} \leq \hat{\rho}, i \in \mathcal{I} \quad (20d)$$

In this problem, $\hat{\rho}$ is an auxiliary variable, and by (20d), it takes the value of maximum load over all cells. After solving the problem, if the optimal $\hat{\rho}$ is less than or equal to $\bar{\rho}$, action $\{D_i^t | i \in \mathcal{I}\}$ is feasible.

The multi-cell problem (20) concerns a single time slot. However, we have to deal with the cells' interdependence in interference and the resulting non-convexity. To proceed, we consider local optimization of the symbol vector within each cell, that is, each cell finds the solution that maximizes the SINR of each of its users (even though the solution does not mean minimum interference to other cell users). This is a reasonable trade-off, because the solution is locally optimal within each cell, and maximum SINR translates into minimum resource consumption, which reduces interference to other cells. Moreover, the computation becomes confined within each individual cell.

Consider cell i and user $j \in \mathcal{J}_i$. To maximize the SINR by optimizing \mathbf{x}_{ij} , the problem is formulated as

$$\max \quad \|\mathbf{H}_{ij}\mathbf{x}_{ij}\|^2 \quad (21a)$$

$$\text{o.v. } \mathbf{x}_{ij}$$

$$\text{s.t. } \text{Tr}(\mathbf{x}_{ij}\mathbf{x}_{ij}^T) = N_T \quad (21b)$$

To solve (21), we use singular value decomposition (SVD) to deal with the channel matrix, i.e., $\mathbf{H}_{ij} = \mathbf{U}_{ij}\mathbf{\Sigma}_{ij}\mathbf{V}_{ij}^T$, creating multiple independent virtual SISO subchannels. Subsequently, we employ the well-known water-filling algorithm [43] for $\mathbf{\Sigma}_{ij}$ to determine the optimal signal vector \mathbf{x}_{ij}^* . Then, the PCBS uses right singular matrix \mathbf{V}_{ij} for precoding, transforming the signal into the subchannels. The user uses left singular matrix \mathbf{U}_{ij} for post-processing, decoupling the received signal into independent subchannel signals.

5.2 Multi-cell Optimization and Reward Design

Having computed $\mathbf{x}_{ij}^*, j \in \mathcal{J}_i, i \in \mathcal{I}$, the problem becomes more tractable. More specifically, the interference term Φ_{ij} takes the following form

$$\Phi_{ij} = \frac{E}{N_T} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{J}_\ell} \rho_{\ell k} h_{\ell k j}, \quad (22)$$

where $h_{\ell k j} = \|\mathbf{H}_{\ell k}\mathbf{x}_{\ell k}^*\|^2$. In addition, we define $h_{ij} = \|\mathbf{H}_{ij}\mathbf{x}_{ij}^*\|^2$. Plugging in the above into (4), and let $N_c = \frac{BN_0N_T}{E}$, the problem reads

$$\min \quad \hat{\rho} \quad (23a)$$

$$\text{o.v. } \hat{\rho}, \rho_{ij}, i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}_i$$

$$\text{s.t. } \rho_{ij} B \log \left[1 + \frac{h_{ij}}{\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{J}_\ell} \rho_{\ell k} h_{\ell k j} + N_c} \right] \geq \frac{D_i}{|\mathcal{J}_i|}, \quad j \in \mathcal{J}_i, i \in \mathcal{I} \quad (23b)$$

$$\rho_i = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \rho_{ij} \leq \hat{\rho}, i \in \mathcal{I} \quad (23c)$$

Lemma 2. *There exists at least one optimal solution of (23), such that (23b) holds as equality for all users.*

Proof. Denote by ρ^* an optimal solution, and suppose for this solution (23b) holds as strict inequality for user $j \in \mathcal{J}_i$. Clearly, we can reduce ρ_{ij}^* slightly without violating (23b) for this user. Moreover, a smaller value of ρ_{ij} implies less interference (i.e., smaller value of the SINR denominator for any user in other cells), and hence (23b) remains to hold for all the other users, and the lemma follows. \square

Define $\boldsymbol{\rho}_{-ij} = [\rho_{\ell k} | \ell \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i\}, k \in \mathcal{J}_\ell]$. This is the vector of all user-level load (i.e., resource consumption) for meeting user throughput in cells other than i . Moreover, let $f_{ij}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_{-ij})$ denote the value of ρ_{ij} as function of $\boldsymbol{\rho}_{-ij}$, that is,

$$f_{ij}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_{-ij}) = \frac{D_i}{B|\mathcal{J}_i| \log \left[1 + \frac{h_{ij}}{\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{J}_\ell} \rho_{\ell k} h_{\ell k j} + N_c} \right]}. \quad (24)$$

Algorithm 1: Fixed-point method

Input: $\{D_i, \mathbf{x}_{ij}^*, i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}_i\}, \varepsilon;$
Output: $\hat{\rho};$
1 Initialize $\boldsymbol{\rho}^{(0)};$
2 $\tau \leftarrow 0;$
3 **repeat**
4 $\tau \leftarrow \tau + 1;$
5 **for** cell $i, i \in \mathcal{I}$ **do**
6 **for** user $i, j \in \mathcal{J}_i$ **do**
7 $\rho_{ij}^\tau \leftarrow f_{ij}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_{-ij}^{(\tau-1)})$
8 **until** $\|\boldsymbol{\rho}^{(\tau)} - \boldsymbol{\rho}^{(\tau-1)}\|_\infty \leq \varepsilon;$
9 $\hat{\rho} = \max_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \rho_{ij}^{(\tau)};$
10 **return** $\hat{\rho};$

By Lemma 2, what we are seeking is the solution to the following system.

$$\rho_{ij} = f_{ij}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_{-ij}) \quad (25)$$

Lemma 3. *Function $f_{ij}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_{-ij}), j \in \mathcal{J}_i, i \in \mathcal{I}$ is a standard interference function (SIF).*

Proof. See Appendix A. \square

Theorem 4. *Let $\rho_{ij}^{(0)} \geq 0$ ($j \in \mathcal{J}_i, i \in \mathcal{I}$) be an arbitrary non-negative initial point. Then, the fixed-point method, where $\rho_{ij}^{(\tau+1)} = f_{ij}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_{-ij}^{(\tau)}), \tau = 0, 1, \dots$, converges to a unique point that is optimum of (23).*

Proof. The fixed-point iterations converge to a unique point follows from the basic properties of SIF [44, Theorems 1 and 2]. This together with Lemma 2 establish the theorem. \square

The fixed-point method for solving (23) is given in Algorithm 1. It is noted that when using (24) to make updates, the complexity of interference computation is proportional to the number of users of the entire system. The complexity is greatly reduced if the interference computation involves cell-level information only. To this end, we present two interference approximations.

- 1) Long range approximation: Assuming significant inter-cell distance, resulting in low diversity in the MIMO channel, $\mathbf{H}_{\ell j}$ is approximated as a rank-1 matrix. Interference from cell ℓ at user j in cell i is approximated by $\rho_\ell E |g_{\ell j}|^2$, where ρ_ℓ is the cell-level load of ℓ and $g_{\ell j}$ is the singular value of the MIMO channel obtained through SVD, with $\mathbf{H}_{\ell j} = \mathbf{u} g_{\ell j} \mathbf{v}^T$. Here, \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} are unitary orthogonal vectors representing the receiving and transmitting spaces, respectively.
- 2) Upper bound approximation: For $j \in \mathcal{J}_i$, an upper bound of interference from cell ℓ can be obtained by the SVD and water-filling algorithm applied to (26).

$$\max \quad \|\mathbf{H}_{\ell j}\mathbf{x}_{\ell j}\|^2 \quad (26a)$$

$$\text{o.v. } \mathbf{x}_{\ell j}$$

$$\text{s.t. } \text{Tr}(\mathbf{x}_{\ell j}\mathbf{x}_{\ell j}^T) = N_T \quad (26b)$$

Let $\|\mathbf{H}_{\ell j} \mathbf{x}_{\ell j}^{\star}\|^2$ be the maximum value of (26). Clearly, $\rho_{\ell} \frac{E}{N_T} \|\mathbf{H}_{\ell j} \mathbf{x}_{\ell j}^{\star}\|^2$ is an upper bound of interference. Therefore, $\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{I}, \ell \neq i} \rho_{\ell} \frac{E}{N_T} \|\mathbf{H}_{\ell j} \mathbf{x}_{\ell j}^{\star}\|^2$ represents an upper bound of the total interference received by user j .

By either of the approximations, the interference experienced by user $j \in \mathcal{J}_i$ due to another cell ℓ is a function in the cell-level load ρ_{ℓ} . Letting $\boldsymbol{\rho}_{-i} = [\rho_1, \rho_2, \dots, \rho_{i-1}, \rho_{i+1}, \dots, \rho_I]$, the resulting system equation is $\rho_i = f_i(\boldsymbol{\rho}_{-i}) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} f_{ij}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_{-i}), i \in \mathcal{I}$.

Theorem 5. Function $f_i(\boldsymbol{\rho}_{-i})$ for either of the approximations is an SIF.

Proof. See Appendix B. \square

After obtaining $\hat{\rho}$ by fixed-point method for solving (23) or any of the approximations, we verify whether or not it is below the resource limit $\bar{\rho}$, i.e.,

$$\hat{\rho} \leq \bar{\rho}. \quad (27)$$

If the condition is met, the action, namely the throughput $D_i, i \in \mathcal{I}$, is admitted. In this case, the reward with respect to cell i equals D_i . Otherwise, the action is denied and the reward becomes zero. That is,

$$R_{\rho_i}(s_t, a_t) = \begin{cases} D_i & \text{if (27) holds} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

6 REWARD DESIGN FOR TEMPERATURE LIMIT

The exploration phase in RL comes with the risk of overheating. We design a reward system to make temperature stay within the limit while providing the agent with accurate feedback. The policy zone, denoted by Π , is defined as:

$$\Pi = \left\{ \pi | \Psi_i^t + \lambda_i \delta \mathbb{E}_{\sigma_i^t, D_i^t \sim \pi(\cdot | s_t)} \left[\mu_i D_i^t + \alpha_i e^{\beta_i \Psi_i^t} + \gamma_i - \sigma_i^t (\Psi_i^t - \hat{\Psi}_i^t) \right] \leq \bar{\Psi}, i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T} \right\}. \quad (29)$$

In addition, we introduce a temperature parameter $\Psi_i^{t, \text{risk}}$, of which the value shall be as large as possible, subject to the following condition. By the condition, at temperature $\Psi_i^{t, \text{risk}}$, the expected temperature will not exceed the maximum allowed value in the next time slot, even if the agent takes the action of maximum throughput.

$$\Psi_i^{t, \text{risk}} + \lambda_i \delta \mathbb{E}_{\sigma_i^t} \left[\mu_i D_{\max} + \alpha_i e^{\beta_i \Psi_i^t} + \gamma_i - \sigma_i^t (\Psi_i^t - \hat{\Psi}_i^t) \right] \leq \bar{\Psi}, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, i \in \mathcal{I} \quad (30)$$

In our reward mechanism, we operate across the policies and let the system react with different rewards and decisions. Fig. 2 illustrates the temperature range of policy zone Π and the proposed reward structure. Specifically, for an action of time slot t , the system assesses the baseband processor's temperature evolution, namely Ψ_i^{t+1} and, responds as follows:

- $\Psi_i^{t+1} > \bar{\Psi}$: The action is denied to prevent overheating, and a penalty (i.e., negative reward) is set.
- $\Psi_i^{t, \text{risk}} < \Psi_i^{t+1} \leq \bar{\Psi}$: In this case, there is no overheating but the condition (30) is not met. The action

Fig. 2: An illustration of the reward mechanism based on the thermal performance.

is permitted, with a throughput reward that is, however, reduced (i.e., a penalty term is added).

- $\Psi_i^{t+1} \leq \Psi_i^{t, \text{risk}}$: In this case, the temperature is in the safe range. The action is permitted, and the agent receives a positive reward for the throughput.

This mechanism ensures that the agent can learn to balance between the performance objectives in thermal management and throughput. However, risk condition (30) is implicit to the agent when we implement SAC, as computing the expectations above requires knowing π , and π is not learned yet. We need to compute an explicit value of $\Psi_i^{t, \text{risk}}$. For time slot t and cell i , we use Ψ to represent the temperature, and this temperature can be represented using an optimization problem as follows.

$$\Psi_i^{t, \text{risk}} = \max_{\pi} \Psi \quad (31a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \Psi + \lambda_i \delta \mathbb{E}_{\sigma_i^t} \left[\mu_i D_i^t + \alpha_i e^{\beta_i \Psi} + \gamma_i - \sigma_i^t (\Psi - \hat{\Psi}_i^t) \right] \leq \bar{\Psi} \quad (31b)$$

Constraint (31b) states if D_i^t is applied, then the resulting temperature Ψ_i^{t+1} in the next time slot may not exceed the limit $\bar{\Psi}$. Solving the optimization problem exactly requires knowledge of the distribution of the heat dissipation efficiency as well as the learned policy distribution, which are not available a priori. We use the following approximation to solve problem (31):

$$\begin{aligned} & \Psi + \lambda_i \delta \mathbb{E}_{\sigma_i^t, D_i^t \sim \pi(\cdot | s_t)} \left[\mu_i D_i^t + \alpha_i e^{\beta_i \Psi} + \gamma_i - \sigma_i^t (\Psi - \hat{\Psi}_i^t) \right] \\ & \leq \Psi + \lambda_i \delta \mathbb{E}_{\sigma_i^t} \left[\mu_i D_{\max} + \alpha_i e^{\beta_i \Psi} + \gamma_i - \sigma_i^t (\Psi - \hat{\Psi}_i^t) \right] \\ & \approx \Psi + \lambda_i \delta \left[\mu_i D_{\max} + \alpha_i e^{\beta_i \Psi} + \gamma_i - \bar{\sigma}_i^t (\Psi - \hat{\Psi}_i^t) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_i^t$ represents the estimated heat dissipation efficiency for time slot t and cell i . Several methods are available for doing the estimation. For instance, one might employ historical average values or resort to the most conservative estimates, such as the worst value recorded in history. Hence, problem (31) can be approximated as

$$\Psi_i^{t, \text{risk}} = \max_{\pi} \Psi \quad (33a)$$

Algorithm 2: Reward mechanism in time slot t

Input: $\{D_i^t, \hat{\Psi}_i^t, \sigma_i^t, i \in \mathcal{I}\}$
Output: $\{D_i^t, \Psi_i^{t+1}, i \in \mathcal{I}\}, R_t$

- 1 Calculate $\hat{\rho}$ by Algorithm 1
- 2 **if** $\hat{\rho} > \bar{\rho}$ **then**
- 3 **for** cell $i, i \in \mathcal{I}$ **do**
- 4 $D_i^t \leftarrow 0$
- 5 **for** cell $i, i \in \mathcal{I}$ **do**
- 6 Obtain $\Psi_i^{t,\text{risk}}$ by solving (33) via bi-section search
- 7 $\hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1} \leftarrow$
 $\Psi_i^t + \lambda_i \delta \left[\mu_i D_i^t + \alpha_i e^{\beta_i \Psi_i^t} + \gamma_i - \bar{\sigma}_i^t (\Psi_i^t - \hat{\Psi}_i^t) \right]$
- 8 **if** $\hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1} > \bar{\Psi}$ **then**
- 9 $D_i^t \leftarrow 0$
- 10 $\Psi_i^{t+1} \leftarrow \Psi_i^t + \lambda_i \delta \left[\alpha_i e^{\beta_i \Psi_i^t} + \gamma_i - \bar{\sigma}_i^t (\Psi_i^t - \hat{\Psi}_i^t) \right]$
- 11 $R_{\Psi_i} \leftarrow \bar{\Psi} - \hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1}$
- 12 **else if** $\Psi_i^{t,\text{risk}} \leq \hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1} < \bar{\Psi}$ **then**
- 13 $\Psi_i^{t+1} \leftarrow \hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1}$
- 14 $R_{\Psi_i} \leftarrow \frac{D_i^t}{\text{std}(\{D_i^t, i \in \mathcal{I}\})} + \Psi_i^{t,\text{risk}} - \hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1}$
- 15 **else**
- 16 $\Psi_i^{t+1} \leftarrow \hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1}$
- 17 $R_{\Psi_i} \leftarrow \frac{D_i^t}{\text{std}(\{D_i^t, i \in \mathcal{I}\})}$
- 18 $R_t \leftarrow \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} R_{\Psi_i}$
- 19 **return** $\{D_i^t, \Psi_i^{t+1}, i \in \mathcal{I}\}, R_t$

$$\text{s.t. } \Psi + \lambda_i \delta \left[\mu_i D_{\max} + \alpha_i e^{\beta_i \Psi} + \gamma_i - \bar{\sigma}_i^t (\Psi - \hat{\Psi}_i^t) \right] \leq \bar{\Psi} \quad (33b)$$

Note that (33) can be efficiently solved using a bi-section search. Next, with the derived $\Psi_i^{t,\text{risk}}$, we use the reward function for cell i as follows.

$$R_{\Psi_i}(s_t, a_t) = \begin{cases} R_{\rho_i}(s_t, a_t) & \hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1} < \Psi_i^{t,\text{risk}} \\ R_{\rho_i}(s_t, a_t) + \Psi_i^{t,\text{risk}} - \hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1} & \Psi_i^{t,\text{risk}} \leq \hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1} < \bar{\Psi} \\ \hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1} - \bar{\Psi} & \hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1} \geq \bar{\Psi} \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

where $\hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1}$ is an estimated temperature. The reward function $R_{\Psi_i}(s_t, a_t)$ described above is a piecewise function based on the estimated temperature $\hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1}$, $\Psi_i^{t,\text{risk}}$, and the limit $\bar{\Psi}$. The decision made by (34) follows the general idea outlined earlier. There are three additional specifics, however. First, the reward (i.e., $R_{\rho_i}(s_t, a_t)$) is positive only if the action meets the resource limit (cf. (28)). Second, since we cannot obtain exact value of Ψ_i^{t+1} , estimated temperature value $\hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1}$ is used in lieu. Third, the penalty is set to be how much the estimated temperature exceeds the risk level $\Psi_i^{t,\text{risk}}$ or the limit $\bar{\Psi}$.

The flow of the entire reward mechanism, with respect to both the resource and temperature limits, is shown in Algorithm 2. Note that for the UHD scenario, we use the estimated value $\bar{\sigma}_i^t$ as the input of σ_i^t .

7 SOFT ACTOR-CRITIC (SAC) LEARNING

The state value function $Q(s_t, a_t)$ and the action-state value function $V(s_t)$ of the SAC are defined as follows:

$$Q(s_t, a_t) = R(s_t, a_t) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{s_{t+1} \sim p(\cdot | s_t, a_t)} [V(s_{t+1})], \quad (35)$$

$$V(s_t) = \mathbb{E}_{a_t \sim \pi} [Q(s_t, a_t) - k \log(\pi(a_t | s_t))]. \quad (36)$$

We employ function approximators for the policy function, the V-function, and the Q-function. Our approach includes a tractable policy $\pi_\phi(a_t | s_t)$, a parameterized state value function $V_\psi(s_t)$, and a soft Q-function $Q_\theta(s_t, a_t)$. Here, ϕ , ψ , and θ denote network parameters. Our algorithm integrates three DNN types: V-network, Q-network, and policy network. Stochastic gradient descent is used to optimize the networks iteratively.

To detail the parameter updates, we first focus on the update of the soft value that comes from the approximation of the state value function. The soft value function is trained by minimizing the squared residual error

$$J_V(\psi) = \mathbb{E}_{s_t \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\frac{1}{2} \left((V_\psi(s_t) - \mathbb{E}_{a_t \sim \pi_\phi} [Q_\theta(s_t, a_t) - \log \pi_\phi(a_t | s_t)])^2 \right) \right], \quad (37)$$

where \mathcal{D} is a replay buffer. Then, the gradient of the equation (37) is estimated using an unbiased estimator

$$\hat{\nabla}_\psi J_V(\psi) = \nabla_\psi V_\psi(s_i) [V_\psi(s_t) - Q_\theta(s_t, a_t) + \log \pi_\phi(a_t | s_t)], \quad (38)$$

wherein actions are chosen from the current policy set.

Furthermore, the soft Q-function parameter is trained by minimizing the following soft Bellman residual:

$$J_Q(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{(s_t, a_t) \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(Q_\theta(s_t, a_t) - \hat{Q}(s_t, a_t) \right)^2 \right], \quad (39)$$

with $\hat{Q}(s_t, a_t) = R(s_t, a_t) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{s_{t+1} \sim p} [V_{\bar{\psi}}(s_{t+1})]$. We use the following stochastic gradients to optimize (39):

$$\hat{\nabla}_\theta J_Q(\theta) = \nabla_\theta Q_\theta(a_t, s_t) \left(Q_\theta(s_t, a_t) - R(s_t, a_t) - \gamma V_{\bar{\psi}}(s_{t+1}) \right), \quad (40)$$

where a target value network $V_{\bar{\psi}}$ is used for updates. We update the target weights to match the current value function weights periodically, i.e.,

$$\bar{\psi} \leftarrow \tau \psi + (1 - \tau) \bar{\psi}, \quad (41)$$

where τ is a target smoothing coefficient to improve stability. Finally, the policy parameter is learned by minimizing the expected Kullback-Leibler divergence:

$$J_\pi(\phi) = \mathbb{E}_{s_t \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\text{D}_{\text{KL}} \left(\pi_\phi(\cdot | s_t) \left\| \frac{\exp(Q_\theta(s_t, \cdot))}{Z_\theta(s_t)} \right\| \right) \right]. \quad (42)$$

We use neural network transformation to reparameterize the policy, i.e.,

$$a_i = g_\phi(\epsilon_t; s_t), \quad (43)$$

where ϵ_t is a noise vector. The objective can be rewritten as

$$J_\pi(\phi) = \mathbb{E}_{s_t \sim \mathcal{D}, \epsilon_t \sim \mathcal{N}} [\log \pi_\phi(g_\phi(\epsilon_t; s_t) | s_t)]$$

Algorithm 3: Training for the SAC-based method

Input: $\psi, \bar{\psi}, \phi, \theta_1, \theta_2$
Output: Trained policy $\pi_\phi(a_t|s_t)$

- 1 Set learning rates λ_V, λ_Q , and λ_π for V-network, Q-network, and policy network, respectively
- 2 Initialize $\psi, \bar{\psi}, \phi, \theta_1, \theta_2$ and experience memory \mathcal{D}
- 3 **for each episode do**
- 4 **for each environment step do**
- 5 $a_t \sim \pi_\phi(a_t|s_t)$
- 6 $s_{t+1} \sim p(s_{t+1}|s_t, a_t)$
- 7 Obtain reward R_t by Algorithm 2
- 8 $\mathcal{D} \leftarrow \mathcal{D} \cup \{(s_t, a_t, R_t, s_{t+1})\}$
- 9 **for each gradient step do**
- 10 Sample from current policy and compute $\hat{\nabla}_\psi J_V(\psi)$ by (38)
- 11 Update V-network parameter:
 $\psi \leftarrow \psi - \lambda_V \hat{\nabla}_\psi J_V(\psi)$
- 12 Sample from \mathcal{D} and compute $\nabla J_Q(\theta_n), n \in \{1, 2\}$ by (40)
- 13 Update dual Q-network parameters:
 $\theta_n \leftarrow \theta_n - \lambda_Q \hat{\nabla}_{\theta_n} J_Q(\theta_n), n \in \{1, 2\}$
- 14 Sample from the fixed distribution and compute $\hat{\nabla}_\phi J_\pi(\phi)$ by (45)
- 15 Update policy network parameter:
 $\phi \leftarrow \phi - \lambda_\pi \hat{\nabla}_\phi J_\pi(\phi)$
- 16 Update the target value network parameters:
 $\bar{\psi} \leftarrow \tau \psi + (1 - \tau) \bar{\psi}$
- 17 **return** $\pi_\phi(a_t|s_t)$

$$-Q_\theta(s_t, g_\phi(\epsilon_t; s_t))]. \quad (44)$$

The gradient of (44) can be approximated as

$$\hat{\nabla}_\phi J_\pi(\phi) = (\nabla_{a_t} \log \pi_\phi(a_t|s_t) - \nabla_{a_t} Q(s_t, a_t)) \nabla_\phi g_\phi(\epsilon_t; s_t) + \nabla_\phi \log \pi_\phi(a_t|s_t). \quad (45)$$

The training algorithm for SAC-based online thermal management for PCBS is summarized in Algorithm 3. Note that dual Q-networks are employed to mitigate positive bias during policy enhancement. Specifically, parameters θ_1 and θ_2 are used to shape two distinct Q-functions. They are trained individually, optimizing soft Bellman residual with parameters $J_Q(\theta_1)$ and $J_Q(\theta_2)$. Upon convergence, we obtain an online throughput management policy $\pi_\phi(a_t|s_t)$.

7.1 Overview of the proposed RL framework

We provide the following details of the proposed RL framework.

1) **Initialization:** The algorithm begins by initializing the policy network $\pi_\phi(a_t|s_t)$, two Q-networks $Q_{\theta_1}(s_t, a_t)$ and $Q_{\theta_2}(s_t, a_t)$, the value network $V_\psi(s_t)$, and the target value network $V_{\bar{\psi}}(s_t)$. A replay buffer \mathcal{D} is also initialized to store experience tuples collected during the interaction with the environment.

2) **Fixed-point method for resource allocation:** In each time slot t , the fixed-point method given in Algorithm 1 is used to solve the resource allocation problem across multiple cells. The load variable ρ_{ij} for each cell i and user j is initialized, and iterative updates are performed using the following equation:

$$\rho_{ij}^{(\tau+1)} = f_{ij}(\rho_{-ij}^{(\tau)}) \quad (46)$$

This process is repeated until the load values converge. The maximum load $\hat{\rho}$ across all cells is then computed. If $\hat{\rho}$ exceeds the predefined resource limit $\bar{\rho}$, the action D_i^t for all cells is set to be zero, indicating that the resource constraint is violated.

3) **Reward mechanism in time slot t :** For thermal management, the reward mechanism operates by evaluating the agent's action based on the temperature evolution of the system. For each cell i , the risk temperature $\Psi_i^{t, \text{risk}}$ is computed by solving (33). The agent then estimates the future temperature $\hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1}$ based on the current action D_i^t and environmental dynamics. The reward $R_{\Psi_i}(s_t, a_t)$ is assigned based on the following conditions:

- If $\hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1} \leq \Psi_i^{t, \text{risk}}$, the action is allowed, and a positive reward based on throughput is provided.
- If $\Psi_i^{t, \text{risk}} < \hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1} \leq \bar{\Psi}$, the action is allowed but with a reduced reward.
- If $\hat{\Psi}_i^{t+1} > \bar{\Psi}$, the action is denied, and a negative reward is given to penalize overheating.

The total reward R_t for time slot t is the sum of the rewards across all cells.

4) **SAC training process:** The SAC training process is executed for each environment interaction. The agent observes the current state s_t and samples an action $a_t \sim \pi_\phi(a_t|s_t)$ from the policy network. The environment transitions to the next state s_{t+1} , and the reward R_t is received. The transition (s_t, a_t, R_t, s_{t+1}) is stored in the replay buffer \mathcal{D} . Periodically, mini-batches are sampled from the replay buffer to update the networks:

- **V-network update:** The value network $V_\psi(s_t)$ is updated by minimizing the value function error using the soft value update rule.
- **Q-network update:** The two Q-networks Q_{θ_1} and Q_{θ_2} are updated by minimizing the soft Bellman residual.
- **Policy network update:** The policy network $\pi_\phi(a_t|s_t)$ is optimized by minimizing the Kullback-Leibler divergence between the policy and the Q-function.
- **Target network update:** The target value network $V_{\bar{\psi}}$ is updated using a soft update rule:

$$\bar{\psi} \leftarrow \tau \psi + (1 - \tau) \bar{\psi} \quad (47)$$

5) **Policy deployment without pretraining:** Since our proposed reward mechanism can protect the processors from overheating, the RL framework can be deployed without any pretraining. After a short period of train-

ing after deployment, the learned policy $\pi_\phi(a_t|s_t)$ will handle online throughput and thermal management for the multi-cell system.

In applying the proposed RL framework to our problem, several key steps ensure that interference and thermal constraints are effectively managed. First, interference is handled by modeling the load of each cell and its associated users as described in (20). SAC optimizes the SINR at the user level by finding the optimal MIMO transmission vector that maximizes the SINR within each cell. As described in the reward mechanism, i.e., Algorithm 2 embedded with Algorithm 1, if the load violates the resource constraint (27), SAC penalizes the action, ensuring that the policy learns to allocate resources without exceeding the capacity.

For thermal management, we use a risk-aware reward mechanism that incorporates a temperature threshold $\bar{\Psi}$ and an estimated risk level $\Psi_i^{t,\text{risk}}$ for each cell, as defined in (30) and (31). This risk level ensures that the policy avoids overheating by dynamically adjusting throughput and controlling processor temperature. Actions that would lead to excessive heat are penalized, while actions that maintain temperatures within safe limits are rewarded. SAC’s entropy regularization further supports this balance by encouraging the exploration of throughput configurations that meet performance goals without violating thermal constraints. The policy thus learns efficient thermal management over time, adapting to varying ambient temperatures and cell loads. By integrating both interference and thermal objectives into the reward structure, SAC ensures that the policy converges to a solution that effectively balances resource utilization and thermal limit.

8 SIMULATION RESULTS

The hyperparameters of the proposed SAC scheme and the system model parameters are summarized in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. We use the upper bound approximation introduced in Section 5.2 for performance evaluation because the approximation means we are on the safe side from thermal standpoint.

TABLE 2: SAC hyperparameters

Hyperparameter	Value
Layers	2 fully connected
Layer hidden units	64
Activation function	ReLU
Batch size	256
Replay buffer size	1×10^6
Target smoothing coefficient	0.005
Target update interval	1
Discount rate	0.99
Learning iterations per round	1
Learning rate	3×10^{-4}
Optimizer	Adam
Loss	Mean squared error
Entropy target factor	0.2

TABLE 3: System model parameters

Parameter	Value
Number of PCBs I	7
Number of users per cell J_i	100
Number of time slots T	100
Bandwidth of one RB B	180kHz
Safe temperature $\bar{\Psi}$	120°C
Maximum throughput D^{\max}	100 Mbps
Heat dissipation distribution	$\sigma \sim U[0.25, 1.25]W/^\circ C$
Average ambient temperature $\bar{\Psi}$	[16, 32]°C
Ambient temperature distribution	$\bar{\Psi} \sim U[0.8\bar{\Psi}, 1.2\bar{\Psi}]^\circ C$
Reciprocal of thermal capacitance λ	0.007°C/J [38]
Throughput/dynamic-power ratio μ	0.6 W/Mbps [40]
Duration of a time slot δ	30 seconds

8.1 Convergence

We assess the convergence of our SAC-based thermal management (SAC-TM) strategy for the UHD scenario, comparing it with three other RL algorithms: Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [45], Advantage Actor-Critic (A2C) [46], which is a synchronous and batched variant of the Asynchronous Advantage Actor-Critic (A3C) [47], and Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) [48]. All four algorithms use the same configuration, including input design and reward functions, as our proposed SAC framework. Fig. 3 presents the average reward over episodes. The key findings are as follows:

- While effective in continuous action spaces, **DDPG** underperforms in our experiments. DDPG is particularly sensitive to hyperparameter tuning, and despite multiple trials of adjustments, we are unable to achieve a consistent average reward curve. The deterministic nature of DDPG’s policy often leads to premature convergence to local optima, thereby limiting effective exploration, especially in complex environments. This sensitivity, combined with its reliance on external noise for exploration, further constrains DDPG’s adaptability in our scenario.
- **A2C** exhibited instability. Its synchronous updates rely on smaller batches of data, which result in more frequent fluctuations in policy updates. Moreover, A2C’s value function estimation is prone to error, further destabilizing policy updates. These factors made A2C less effective for the thermal management and interference constraints in our scenario.
- **PPO** showed relatively strong performance, benefiting from its clipping mechanism, which limits large policy updates. This improves stability and exploration. However, PPO did not outperform SAC, particularly in handling more complex exploration challenges.
- The primary advantage of **SAC** lies in its maximum entropy framework, which promotes more effective exploration by balancing reward maximization with policy entropy. This entropy regularization mechanism helps SAC resist pre-mature convergence, an

Fig. 3: Average reward versus episodes using four RL algorithms under UHD scenario. (The average ambient temperature is 24°C and the average heat dissipation efficiency is 0.75.)

issue often encountered with DDPG due to its deterministic policy. In addition, SAC outperforms PPO in high-dimensional, continuous action tasks by maintaining a more robust exploration strategy, which is particularly beneficial in complex scenarios like thermal management. Unlike PPO, which relies on clipping for stability, SAC’s off-policy nature improves sample efficiency through a replay buffer. Furthermore, SAC’s automatic entropy tuning dynamically adjusts the balance between exploration and exploitation, enhancing its adaptability. These features made SAC the most effective choice in our experiments, especially within complex and uncertain environments.

8.2 Policy Performance Evaluation

Given the poor performance of A2C and DDPG, we focus our next assessment on the effectiveness of the SAC-TM and PPO-based thermal management (PPO-TM) policies, comparing them to a benchmark referred to as the Oracle. In Oracle, the global optimum is computed offline by convex optimization tools, such as CVX [49], by assuming prior knowledge of complete information across all time slots. Fig. 4 shows that the average throughput per cell with respect to the (average) ambient temperature. The average is taken for 1000 instances for each value of average ambient temperature. The results clearly demonstrate that SAC-TM achieves very good performance, and outperforms PPO-TM. For an average ambient temperature of 16°C, the policy yields 86.9% and 82.6% of the global optimum for the IHD and UHD scenarios, respectively. Higher ambient temperature results in lower throughput as expected, but the (absolute) throughput difference to the global optimum remains largely the same.

For the IHD scenario, Fig. 5 illustrates the maximum baseband processor’s temperature (of all seven PCBs) and the total throughput under three policies: SAC-TM, PPO-TM, and a naive adaptive policy (cf. Section 3.2) for one data instance. For each time slot, this policy considers the maximum cell-uniform throughput that is permitted by the

Fig. 4: Throughput per cell with respect to the average ambient temperature. (The average heat dissipation efficiency is 0.75.)

resource constraint. This throughput level is used if the resulting temperature by the end of the time slot is within the limit for all cells; otherwise, the policy takes no action to let the baseband processor cool down. Overall, SAC-TM clearly outperforms the other two. With SAC-TM, the temperature stays close but below the limit. With the naive adaptive policy, the temperature clearly has more fluctuations, and the throughput is considerably lower than that via SAC-TM. PPO-TM performance is somewhere between SAC-TM and the native adaptive policy.

8.3 Reward Mechanism Assessment

A basic reward function for our problem is simply letting the reward equal the total throughput, i.e., $R(s_t, a_t) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} D_i^t$. In Fig. 6, we compare this basic reward function to the one proposed in Section 6, by showing the agent’s longevity in terms of steps taken in the UHD scenario in the training session. For each training session, the step count is 100. The training concludes prematurely if the agent’s actions breach the temperature constraint (15c) or the resource constraint (15f). Our designed reward function enables the agent to consistently achieve an average of 100 steps of longevity, whereas SAC with the basic reward function, referred to as the naive SAC; fails to reach this number even after 100,000 episodes. This underscores the effectiveness of the proposed SAC in guiding the agent. Note that the performance curve of the proposed SAC shows slight fluctuation between the 35,000th and 40,000th episodes. This is due to the UHD scenario, where the agent has to rely on the estimation of heat dissipation efficiency. There exists a possibility that the actual temperature development may exceed the estimated one, potentially leading to overheating. Table 4 presents the overheating rate and throughput for the two policies for 1000 instances. The results demonstrate that the proposed SAC is superior.

8.4 Generalization for Mobility

The proposed RL is intended for online use, and hence it will continuously learn and adapt the policy to user mobility. Nevertheless, it is of significance to examine how

Fig. 5: The maximum processor temperature of all PCBs evolution and the total accumulated throughput under three evaluated thermal management policies with IHD scenario when the average heat dissipation efficiency is 0.75 and the average ambient temperature is 24°C.

Fig. 6: Average reward versus episodes under IHD scenario. (The average ambient temperature is 24°C and the average heat dissipation efficiency is 0.75.)

Fig. 7: Performance comparison of initial and updated policies for varying levels of user position changes, highlighting the impact of mobility on performance and the system’s adaptability.

TABLE 4: Results for verifying the proposed mechanism

	Proposed SAC	Naive SAC
Overheating Rate	0.1%	12.5%
Throughput (Mbps)	33.2	24.1

well a learned policy generalizes with respect to mobility. To evaluate this aspect, we compare the performance of a policy for a new scenario where some users’ positions are changed, versus that of training a specific model tailored to the new scenario, for various degrees of user mobility. The mobility levels is quantified in the percentage of cell diameter. That is, all users move in some random direction, with a distance specified in percentage of cell diameter. The results are presented in Fig. 7 for a representative instance. For up to 15% of the mobility levels, the initial policy works well in throughput as well as the risk of overheating. Thus, the proposed scheme is sufficiently robust for online learning and decision-making.

Given the model’s ability to generalize well for mobility levels up to 15%, we aim to evaluate how quickly the proposed RL framework can adapt to scenarios with higher mo-

bility levels, specifically at levels of 20% and 25%. Starting with an initial pre-trained model, we measure the number of episodes required for the model to achieve satisfactory performance in these new scenarios. The results, shown in Fig. 8, indicate that even with a 25% mobility levels, the model reaches 75.8% of its stable performance (i.e., the performance after 2000 episodes) within just 500 episodes. This demonstrates the framework’s ability to rapidly adapt to maintain strong performance in dynamically changing environments.

8.5 Robustness for Sudden Events

To evaluate the robustness of the proposed RL framework, we consider two sudden events related to environmental conditions and traffic.

Let us consider a sudden event, where a PCBs is exposed to direct sunlight, causing its ambient temperature to rise quickly to 40°C during time slots 10-15. As shown in Fig. 9, as the ambient temperature quickly escalates, there is a sudden increase in the processor’s temperature, peaking above 120°C. The system reacts by taking low-throughput actions during time slots 11-16, effectively bringing down the temperature with a safety margin. After the event, the

Fig. 8: Throughput per cell after some training episodes for two large degrees of mobility.

Fig. 10: Temperature evolution and actions of two adjacent PCBSs during a sudden traffic peak event.

Fig. 9: Processor and ambient temperature evolution and actions taken by a PCBS during a sudden ambient temperature spike.

Fig. 11: Convergence of the norm $\|\cdot\|_\infty$ in the fixed-point method for different numbers of users.

processor resumes normal operation, maintaining a safe temperature level.

We also analyze a traffic-related event involving two adjacent PCBSs. In this scenario, we let PCBS 1 experience a bursty traffic, where it is forced to operate for maximum throughput during time slots 10-15. The impact on PCBS 2 is evident, as shown in Fig. 10. Due to the increased inter-cell interference caused by PCBS 1's full action, PCBS 2 reduces its throughput to avoid exceeding its resource limit. Once the traffic peak subsides, both PCBSs stabilize and resume normal performance.

8.6 Efficiency and Scalability

Given the real-time requirements of thermal management in large-scale networks, it is crucial that the optimization method used is both efficient and scalable. At each time step, the optimization problem is solved using Algorithm 1. The work in [50] has shown that the fixed-point method has a geometric speed of convergence. Fig. 11 illustrates the convergence of the norm $\|\rho^{(\tau)} - \rho^{(\tau-1)}\|_\infty$ versus the number of iterations, showing that even in scenarios with a large number of users, the method typically converges in as few as 2 to 4 iterations with a tolerance level of 10^{-2} which is sufficient for the overall performance.

Moreover, the fixed-point method is highly scalable. Fig. 12 compares the execution time of serial and parallel implementations on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4080 Laptop GPU. While the serial implementation shows increased execution time as the number of users rises, the parallel implementation demonstrates efficient scalability with the problem size. Even when the number of users increases from 500 to 3000, the execution time remains under 1 second in the parallel implementation. This scalability makes the method suitable for large-scale and real-time use.

Additionally, SAC's architecture, which trains multiple networks, limits its computational complexity to the training phase. As an off-policy algorithm, SAC can learn from past experiences stored in a replay buffer. This allows asynchronous learning without needing constant interaction with the environment. Although the training phase can be time-consuming, it does not affect real-time performance. Once deployed, the system only needs a lightweight forward pass through the actor network to select actions. Thus, our framework ensures both scalability and real-time feasibility for large-scale network deployments.

9 CONCLUSIONS

For outdoor PCBSs, the trade-off between utilization (i.e., throughput) and thermal development is vital. The online

Fig. 12: Execution time comparison between serial and parallel implementations.

optimization problem we studied presents two challenges: Uncertain (future) heat dissipation and interference coupling. As our main conclusion, provided that the reward mechanism is specifically tailored to the problem, an RL approach based on SAC exhibits strong performance in delivering high throughput while keeping the baseband processor's temperature beneath but close to the maximum limit. In fact, its performance is close to that of offline global optimum, hence there is not much room for improvement. Moreover, the approach generalizes well with respect to mobility, enabling it to be embedded into an online learning and decision-making framework. For future study, one topic of interest is to incorporate additional mechanisms beyond RL itself, such as the integration of RL and robust optimization techniques.

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APPENDIX A PROOF OF LEMMA 3

Proof. First, it is obvious that function $f_{ij}(\rho_{-ij})$ has monotonicity, that is, $f_{ij}(\rho'_{-ij}) \geq f_{ij}(\rho_{-ij})$, if $\rho'_{-ij} \geq \rho_{-ij}$. Next, we show that the function also exhibits the so called scalability property, which requires $\alpha f_{ij}(\rho_{-ij}) > f_{ij}(\alpha \rho_{-ij})$ for any scalar $\alpha > 1$.

Let $\rho^{\Xi} = \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{J}_{\ell}} \rho_{\ell k} h_{\ell k j}$. Then, by the expression of $f_{ij}(\rho_{-ij})$, scalability holds, if

$$\alpha \log \left[1 + \frac{h_{ij}}{\alpha \rho^{\Xi} + N_c} \right] > \log \left[1 + \frac{h_{ij}}{\rho^{\Xi} + N_c} \right]. \quad (48)$$

The above holds if

$$\left[1 + \frac{h_{ij}}{\alpha \rho^{\Xi} + N_c} \right]^{\alpha} > 1 + \frac{h_{ij}}{\rho^{\Xi} + N_c}. \quad (49)$$

By the generalized Bernoulli inequality (with real exponent), we have

$$\left[1 + \frac{h_{ij}}{\alpha \rho^{\Xi} + N_c} \right]^{\alpha} > 1 + \frac{\alpha h_{ij}}{\alpha \rho^{\Xi} + N_c} = 1 + \frac{h_{ij}}{\rho^{\Xi} + N_c}. \quad (50)$$

By comparing the right-hand sides of (49) and (50), we have proven scalability. Hence $f_{ij}(\rho_{-ij})$ is an SIF [44]. \square

APPENDIX B PROOF OF SIF WITH THE APPROXIMATIONS

Proof. With either of the two approximations, we obtain the system of the following form.

$$f_{ij}(\rho_{-i}) = \frac{D_i}{B|\mathcal{J}_i| \log \left[1 + \frac{h_{ij}}{\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i\}} \rho_{\ell} \gamma_{\ell} + B N_0} \right]} \quad (51)$$

For the long range approximation, we have $\gamma_{\ell} = E|g_{\ell j}|^2$, and in the upper bound approximation, $\gamma_{\ell} = \frac{E}{N_T} \|\mathbf{H}_{\ell j} \mathbf{x}_{\ell j}^{\star}\|^2$. It is clear that (51) has a similar (but simpler) structure to (24). The SIF result is then obtained by the same arguments used in the proof of Lemma 3. \square

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